

Analysis of Unsteady Pressure Loads on the Themis T3 Vehicle in Unpropelled Backward Flight

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- SALTO - reusable Strategic Space Launcher Technologies & Operations
- funded by the European Union in the frame of the Horizon Europe programme
- supports the ESA Themis programme
- T1H hop tests
- **Technology maturation for T3 and future launcher configurations**

26

Project
partners

12

Countries
represented

38

Months to reach
the objective

2

Flight test
demonstrations

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Evaluate Unsteady Pressure Loads on the T3 Vehicle for Sub- and Supersonic Flight Conditions

1. Evaluate unsteady root-mean-square (RMS) pressure loads on the vehicle surface
2. Analyze pressure spectra at selected surface locations
3. Assess grid resolution for the scale-resolving simulations (iDDDES)

Numerical Tool: DLR TAU Code

- General purpose CFD code developed by the **DLR Institute of Aerodynamics and Flow Technology**
- 2nd-order **compressible FV Navier-Stokes Solver**
- **Unstructured/hybrid grids**: adaptation, chimera and deformation
- **Various turbulence models**: RANS (1-7 eqn.), LES, (i)DES
- **Validated** for a wide range of flows (sub- to hypersonic)
- Models for **high-temperature thermodynamics**
- Models for **chemically reacting flows** (real-gas and multi-phase thermodynamics, combustion models, thermal relaxation, ...)

Simulation Setup

- **Thermally and calorically perfect gas** $\gamma = 1.4$
- Time-accurate **dual-time-stepping scheme** with $\Delta T = 2 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}$
- Total simulation time $\sim 1.0 \text{ s} \leftrightarrow \Delta f = 1 \text{ Hz}$
- **Low-dissipation low-dispersion (LD2)** central scheme with matrix dissipation
- Improved delayed detached-eddy simulation (**iDDDES**)
- **Hybrid mesh** with 16.6 mio cells (baseline), strongly refined in region of interest
- **Full configuration**

Investigated Operating Conditions: Unpropelled Transonic Glide Phase

Property	Unit	Subsonic baseline	Subsonic fine	Supersonic
Simulation time	S	0.995	1.047	1.118
Mach number	-	0.9	0.9	1.5
Angle of Attack	deg	5	5	5
Wall temperature	K	300	300	300
No of grid points	mio	16.55	36.72	16.62

Data Evaluation Strategy

Surface RMS pressure

$$\frac{p_{\text{RMS}}}{p_{\text{dyn}}} = \frac{\sqrt{\langle (p - \langle p \rangle)^2 \rangle}}{1/2 \rho_{\infty} u_{\infty}^2}$$

Single-point spectra

1. Sample at $f_s = 5$ kHz
2. Low-pass filter at $f_c = 2$ kHz
3. Convert to spectrum with sample-length of 1024 samples

$$Sr = \frac{f \cdot L_{\text{ref}}}{u_{\infty}}$$

$$\text{PSD}' = \text{PSD}(f) \cdot \frac{u_{\infty}}{q_{\infty}^2 \cdot L_{\text{ref}}}$$

Turbulent time scale

1. Calculate auto-correlation
2. Fit parabolic curve
3. Find first zero-crossing

$$C(\tau) = C(k \cdot \Delta T) = \frac{\sum_n p'_{n+k} \cdot p'_n}{\sum_n p_n'^2}$$

with $p' = p - \langle p \rangle$

Qualitative Flow Field Overview: Turbulent Structures Q Isosurfaces

Ma = 0.9

Ma = 1.5

$$Q = Q' \cdot \frac{u_{\infty}^2}{D^2}$$

Qualitative Flow Field Overview: Turbulent Structures Q Isosurfaces

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Q-criterion based on post-shock velocity

Surface RMS Pressure For Ma = 0.9

Surface RMS Pressure For Ma = 1.5

Single-Point Spectra at Outer Nozzle

Simulations at $Ma = 0.9$ and $Ma = 1.5$

- Sampling point $\sim 15\%$ of diameter towards throat
- Nozzle inside: fluctuations 2 orders of magnitude lower than on the outside
- Both spectra dominated by low-frequency contribution up to $Sr = 0.2$
- Otherwise no distinct peaks visible

Single-Point Spectra at Central Nozzle

Simulations at $Ma = 0.9$ and $Ma = 1.5$

- Sampling point $\sim 15\%$ of diameter towards throat
- Lower PSD peaks than for the outer nozzle
- No significant low-frequency contribution here
- Outside: $Ma = 0.9$ and 1.5 very similar
- Inside: Large low-freq peak for $Ma = 1.5$

Evaluation of the Turbulent Time Scale

When are samples statistically independent?

- **Statistic contains all surface points**
- **Average turbulent time scale between 2-2.5 ms**
 - **Only 400 – 500 useable samples per simulation (total ~1 second)**
 - **Probably too low for converged spectrum**
 - **RMS less affected**

How Good is the Grid Resolution for iDDES?

Assessment of a numerical grid sensor

$$S_1 = \frac{k_{res}}{k_{res} + k_{SGS}}$$

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Influence of Mesh Refinement on RMS Pressure

36.7 mio fine mesh vs. 16.6 mio baseline mesh

fine mesh

baseline mesh

Part	Max RMS baseline	Max RMS fine
Baseplate	41.1 %	39.8 %
Nozzle	42.2 %	40.5 %
Body	20.0 %	19.2 %

- **Significantly finer structures visible in Q isosurfaces**
- **Very little influence on RMS distribution**
- **Small differences in the maximum RMS values**
- **Robust setup for RMS pressure estimation**

Conclusion

- **Provided analysis of unsteady pressure loads for the T3 vehicle**
 - Identification of critical regions using RMS pressure maps on the surface
 - Very similar spatial distribution for $Ma = 0.9$ and $Mach = 1.5$ but different amplitude
- **Single-point spectral analysis with limited significance**
 - Sampling statistics worse than initially anticipated
 - Turbulent time scale in the range of 2-2.5 ms reduces sample size drastically
- **Mesh resolution is sufficient on leeward side**
 - Grid sensor successfully applied to this case indicating good resolution
 - RMS pressure values insensitive to grid refinement → robust quantity

Outlook

- **Experimental campaign measuring T3 unsteady aerodynamics conducted at DLR Cologne (Ansgar Marwege):**
 - Comparison between CFD and wind tunnel data
 - Can unsteady wind tunnel CFD data be extrapolated to flight?
- **Comparison of (time-averaged) unsteady simulation results with RANS**
 - Compare global coefficients, e.g. lift, drag, moment coefficients, etc.
 - Transonic regime difficult for RANS models, how large are the errors?

Thank you!

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